

Separation and Determination of Lead(II) by Extraction with Thiobenzoylacetone

M. V. R. MURTI and S. M. KHOPKAR

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay-400 076

Manuscript received 14 February 1977, revised 25 August 1977, accepted 24 February 1978

VARIOUS reagents used for the solvent extraction of lead are dithizone¹, sodiumdiethyldithiocarbamate or cupral², diethylammoniumdithiocarbamate³, K-ethylxanthate⁴, tributylphosphate⁵ and methylisobutylketone⁶. Dithizone is unsuitable due to the presence of diphenylthiocarbazonone as impurity. Amongst β -diketones acetylacetone⁷, dibenzoylmethane⁷, thenoyltrifluoroacetone⁸, thiothenoyltrifluoroacetone⁹ and thiodibenzoylmethane¹⁰ were used as the extractants but none of them were satisfactory as use of either alkaline medium or high reagent concentration was necessary for the purpose of extraction. Thiobenzoylacetone quantitatively extracts lead at pH 8.5–9.1 as a yellow colored complex which can be measured at 390 nm. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective and can be extended for analysis of lead in alloys.

Experimental

Spektromom 204 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with matched 10 mm quartz cells, digital pH meter (ECIL, India, Model pH 822), and Wrist action flask shaker were used.

Thiobenzoylacetone (SBA) was synthesised from benzoylacetone (Fluka, A. G.) by the procedure described earlier⁽¹¹⁾. About $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ SBA in benzene was used. The reagent was preferably preserved in refrigerator.

About 0.8 g of lead nitrate (BDH, AnalaR) was dissolved in 250 ml of distilled water containing 1% nitric acid. The solution was standardized gravimetrically as lead chromate. It contained 1.952 mg/ml of lead. The dilute solution was prepared so as to contain 19.52 μg of lead per ml by hundred fold dilution.

Buffer solution of pH 12.0 was prepared by mixing 10 ml of 0.05 M borax with 12.65 ml of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide.

General Procedure

An aliquot of the solution containing 48.8 μg of lead was taken. After addition of 10 ml of water, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 8.5–9.1. The volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 25 ml. The solution was then transferred to a separatory funnel. 10 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ SBA in benzene was added. The solution was shaken for 15 min. The layers were allowed to settle and separate. After separating the aqueous phase, the yellow coloured

organic phase was shaken for 2 min with 10 ml of buffer solution of pH 12.0 in order to remove the excess reagent. The phases were separated and the absorbance of the coloured complex was measured at 390 nm against the reagent blank prepared similarly. The amount of lead was computed from a calibration graph.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Pb(II)-SBA complex ($\text{Pb} = 2.81 \times 10^{-5} M$) against the reagent blank, and the spectrum of the reagent blank against benzene were recorded. The Pb(II)-SBA complex showed maximum absorbance at 390 nm. The reagent blank showed insignificant absorbance at 390 nm and it was negligible beyond 450 nm. As the absorption maximum of the complex is at 390 nm, all the absorbance measurements were carried out at 390 nm. The molar absorptivity at 390 nm is 1.78×10^4 . The sensitivity (Sandell's definition) is $1.16 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ at 390 nm.

The study of extraction as function of pH showed that the extraction commenced at pH 4.0 and it was quantitative at pH 8.5–9.1. The extraction was incomplete below and above this pH region. Therefore, the optimum pH for quantitative extraction selected was 8.5–9.1. It was noted that lead was not hydrolysed at this pH. The study of effect of salting-out agents such as the nitrates of ammonium, sodium, potassium, magnesium and calcium (1–4 M) showed that there was no effect on the extraction when the nitrates of ammonium, sodium and potassium were used. There was slight decrease in extraction when the nitrates of magnesium and calcium were used possibly due to high ionic concentration.

When different amounts of lead ranging from 12.20–97.60 μg of lead per 10 ml were taken, and extracted at pH 8.5–9.1 with 10 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ SBA in benzene, it was observed that the system adhered to Beer's law in the concentration range of 1.22–9.76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ at 390 nm.

The study of the variation in reagent concentration showed that 10 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ SBA in benzene was sufficient for quantitative extraction of lead. At lower concentrations, the extraction was incomplete whereas at higher concentration of reagent there was insignificant increase in the extraction. The optimum reagent concentration was $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ SBA in benzene. The composition of extracted species was ascertained from the plot of $\log(\text{HSBA})$ against $\log D$ at pH 8.8. A straight line with slope of 2.0 indicated the probable nature of the extracted species as $\text{Pb}(\text{SBA})_2$.

Varying the period of equilibration from 5–30 min revealed that the extraction was incomplete upto 10 min. However, the extraction was quantitative within 15 min. of equilibration. Further the absorbance of the complex was measured at elapsed intervals of 0, 4, 8, 16, 24, 48, 72 hrs. It was observed that the complex

was stable for at least 24 hr. Beyond this time it showed slow degradation.

The effect of several ions on the extraction of lead was studied. The tolerance limit was calculated as described earlier^{1,2}. The results are given in Table.

TABLE — EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Tolerance limit μg	Other ions present
2.0×10^4	Li^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , CN^- , acetate ⁻ , malonate ²⁻ , NO_3^-
1.5×10^4	Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$
1×10^4	Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Br^- , F^- , NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SCN^- , thiourea, $\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}^{4-}$, WO_4^{2-}
4×10^3	VO_2^+ , SeO_3^{2-}
2×10^3	Pt^{4+} , Ir^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , TeO_3^{2-} , SO_3^{2-}
1×10^3	Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , $\text{Pd}^{2+(a)}$, Ce^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Al^{3+}
5×10^2	$\text{Ag}^{+(e)}$, $\text{Hg}^{2+(e)}$, $\text{Cu}^{2+(b)}$, Rh^{3+} , Au^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Be^{2+} , $\text{Co}^{2+(c)}$, $\text{Ni}^{2+(d)}$
2×10^2	Tl^+ , Cd^{2+} , Ru^{3+} , $\text{Zn}^{2+(e)}$, tart ²⁻
1×10^2	Mn^{2+} , cit ³⁻

Selectively extracted with^{1,2} (a) 8-hydroxyquinoline, (b) acetyl-acetone, (c) 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, (d) dimethylglyoxime and (e) masked with alkalicyanide.

Application to the Analysis of Alloys Containing Lead

Lead was determined from the alloys such as gun-metal, solder and TMS alloys by the following procedure. About 0.1 g of the alloy was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid and the tin which was precipitated as metastannic acid was removed and determined gravimetrically. The filtrate and washings were made to 250 ml. A known aliquot of solution was taken and in case copper (II) was present, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5 and copper was removed by selective extraction with 3×10 ml of 0.1 M acetylacetone in benzene. The aqueous phase after the separation of copper containing lead and other ions like zinc and antimony was taken. Zinc was masked with alkalicyanide and the pH of the solution was adjusted to pH 8.5-9.1 to form negatively charged unextractable complexes. Lead (II) was extracted with 10 ml of 1×10^{-3} M benzene and was determined at 390 nm as usual. Antimony (III), if present is not extracted along with lead and therefore does not interfere. The results showed that the recovery of lead in gunmetal was 5.8% and 5.95% against 6.0%. In solder lead was 53.5% and 54.7% as against 55.0% and in TMS alloy lead was 85.0% and 83.3% against 84.6%.

The absorbance of the complex from 20 determinations with $48.8 \mu\text{g}$ of lead was 0.420 ± 0.010 . The relative standard deviation was $\pm 1.2\%$.

References

- O. B. MAHTRE and E. B. SANDELL, *Talanta*, 1964, 11, 295.
- A. M. BULGAKOVA and A. M. VOLKOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1960, 15, 591.
- J. J. WARR and F. CULTITTA, *U. S. Geol. Surv. Profess.*, 1960 Paper No. 400B, 483; *A.A.*, 1961, 8, 2347.
- S. MUKHERJEE, H. K. SAHA and T. CHAKRABARTY, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1974, 269, 122.
- A. A. YADAV and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Talanta*, 1971, 18, 833.
- H. M. N. H. IRVING and A. H. NABILSI, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1968, 41, 505.
- J. STARY and E. HLADKY, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1963, 28, 227.
- V. M. SHINDE and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1967, 1785.
- S. B. AKKI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1972, 45, 167.
- R. R. MULYB and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Chemia. Anali (in press)*.
- M. V. R. MURTI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 455.
- A. K. DE, S. M. KHOPKAR and R. A. CHALMERS, *Solvent Extraction of Metals*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, London, 1970.

Kinetics of Substitution of Mono(Oxalato)Tetra-aquochromium(III) Ion by Orthophosphoric Acid

N. R. ANIPINDI, V. M. RAO and V. ANANTA RAMAM*

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University,
Waltair-530 003.

Manuscript received 9 September 1976, revised 7 October 1977,
accepted 14 March 1978.

IT is observed that the oxalato-complexes of chromium (III) undergo substitution with orthophosphoric acid^{1,2}. In the present communication we report our results obtained in the substitution of mono(oxalato)tetraaquochromium (III) ion by orthophosphoric acid which is relatively faster than the substitution of tris(oxalato)-chromate (III).

Mono(oxalato)tetraaquochromium (III) perchlorate was prepared³, the procedure of which is described here briefly. Equimolar quantities of hexaaquochromium(II) perchlorate and reagent grade sodium oxalate were mixed and kept at 50° for several days. The reaction mixture containing $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^+$ is then adsorbed on a Dowex 50W $\times$ 8 (50-100 mesh) cation exchange resin. It was then selectively eluted from the column with 0.05 M perchloric acid after thoroughly washing the column with double distilled water. The purity of